

OBTAINING ANTI-CORROSION COATINGS FOR OIL PIPELINES

Bekberganova D.D.

Yuldasheva Kh.Sh.

Sapayeva S.G'.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12705251>

Abstract - This article provides information on determining the optimal composition of competitive coatings, as well as studying the effect of various mineral substances and fillers on the composition of gossypol resin and determining the physical and mechanical properties of a new type of coating. The chemical composition, properties, and resistance to various environments of the synthesized optimal composition are studied.

Key words: corrosion, gossypol pitch, competitive coating, corrosion, trunk pipes

INTRODUCTION

Oil and gas production is developing rapidly every year. In 1991, the rate of production of gas condensate with oil in our republic was 2.9 million tons, and by 1999, its rate exceeded 4 million tons. Gas production also grew rapidly, and its production volume in 2002 was 1058.4 billion m³. Currently, the gas production capacity is 67 billion m³. Delivery of these products to consumers is mainly carried out through main oil and gas pipelines and gas networks. They work under the influence of a corrosive active environment (soil electrolyte, currents, bacteria). In such conditions, pipes can corrode and fail quickly. As a result, as mentioned above, it causes great economic difficulties [1; b. 9-10].

To protect metal devices from corrosion, their materials are made of special coating materials or insulating coatings are formed on their surface. But the resulting insulation coatings wear out and break down over time. As a result, moisture containing dissolved salts enters the metal, forms locally corrosive galvanic elements on its surface, and causes corrosion of the object. Corrosion of main pipelines causes huge economic losses. The cost of their production is much higher than the cost of the metal used.

In this work, it is expected to comprehensively solve the problems of efficient use of waste to obtain new modern composite coatings that protect metals from aggressive environments for a long time by using gossypol tar, a waste of the oil industry, various mineral fillers and other local raw materials. Based on this, in the oil and gas sector, the production of means of corrosion protection of metal constructions and transport equipment, ensuring their all-round effect, improving their quality and reducing their cost are urgent issues.

The analysis of the literature revealed that today the composition and technologies of the anti-corrosion coating "Gossi-SM" based on cotton tar have been developed, and such compositions are offered by mass. %: Bitumen BND 60/90-50-60, tar 15-20, low molecular polyethylene, oxyethyl fatty acids of cotton tar as a plasticizer 10-15, wollstanite 5-10. This coating provides optimal corrosion protection of metals by forming a film in an open environment. In addition, it has long-term protection and anti-corrosion properties of external surfaces of pipelines and other metal equipment, including highly aggressive environments [2; b. 111-112].

The coating named "Asmol" has a high protective property and contains sulfoacidic and neutral high-donor functional groups, it can resist any pressure on pipes due to the presence of compounds that ensure the high activity of the metal surfaces of the "Asmol" coating. At the same time, it leads to the slowing down or complete cessation of the electrochemical corrosion process [3; p.34].

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The purpose of the referenced scientific work is to create corrosion protection coatings for oil and gas pipelines, constructions and facilities based on oil industry waste and local raw materials. A number of priorities have been identified to achieve this goal. In our many years of research to create competitive coatings that protect main pipelines from aggressive environments, we have succeeded in creating various composite coatings based on oil refinery cubic residue-cotton tar.

Our preliminary studies were conducted on the effects of mineral and vegetable fillers on gossypol resin at high temperatures (220oC) and the interaction of components in different ratios. Later, lowering the temperature (110-120 o C), we conducted research to determine the effects of H3B03 in the range of 0.5-1%. he formulations were prepared by mixing in a laboratory multifunctional extruder. The adhesion of the resulting anti-corrosion coating was studied. As a result of numerous studies, we managed to obtain coatings that are resistant to acidic and alkaline environments. Test results are presented in tables.

Table 1

Influence of the content of modifying additives on temperature softening and penetration

№	Substances affecting gossypol resin				Melting temperature, °C	Needle penetration depth, mm
	CaO	CH ₄ N ₂ O	Rubber powder	H ₃ BO ₃		
1	0	0	0	0	36,7	210,6
2	0,5	0	0	0	38,4	190,8
3	1	0	0	0	42,3	182,8
4	1,5	0	0	0	47,6	173,4
5	2	0	0	0	49,9	164,2
6	2,5	0	0	0	52,4	152,2
7	3	0	0	0	55,3	141,1
8	3	0,5	0	0	58,7	132,5
9	3	1	0	0	60,9	116,7
10	3	1,5	0	0	63,8	100,4
11	3	2	0	0	66,4	85,1
12	3	2,5	0	0	70,5	70,4
13	3	3	0	0	73,7	55,5
14	3	3	0,5	0	77,6	40,5
15	3	3	1	0	80,9	30,1
16	3	3	1,5	0	88,7	18,3

not

allow achieving the required coating condition.

Table 2

The results of determining the resistance of the coatings synthesized in different proportions to acidic environments

№	Coatings	Initial mass, g	Time, day			Protection level, %		
			1	3	7	HCl	HNO ₃	H ₂ SO ₄
			The mass of the sample change, g					
1	For acidic environments cover	5,56	5,48 5,24 5,52	5,45 5,16 5,47	5,41 5,11 5,44	98,5	98,3	98,4
2	For alkaline environments cover	7,44	6,84	6,85	6,87	Protection level, %		
						NaOH		
						97,4		

From the given results, it can be concluded that the heat and cold tolerance and resistance to different environments of the obtained experimental samples have increased, and we can see that the coating property has appeared.

The testing of this content was carried out according to the requirements of the GOST 51164-98 standard. The obtained composition was tested in water, 3% NaCl solution, hydrochloric and sulfuric acid solutions. The results showed that this composition can act as a new coating in protection against acid corrosion.

References:

1. Хабибуллаев С.Ш., Абибуллаев Д.М., Махманов Ф. М., Бадриддинова Металлар коррозияси ўқув қўлланма Тошкент — «Илм зиё» — 2016.
2. Сақыбаев, Б.А. Получение антикоррозионных покрытий на основе полимеров и хлопковых гудронов для магистральных нефтепроводов: дисс. ... док. философии (ПхД): 6Д072100/ Сақыбаев Берик Абдразакович. – Казахстан., 2019.-111с.
3. Гладких, И.Ф. Разработка нового класса изоляционных материалов для защиты от коррозии подземных газонефтепроводов, обладающих повышенной химической адгезией: автореф. Дисс. ... док. тех. наук: 05.17.03/ Гладких Ирина Фаатовна. – Уфа., 2007.- 34 с.

